

**A STUDY ON STUDENTS PERCEPTION AND ATTITUDE
TOWARDS SELECTING THE PRIVATE COLLEGE
WITH THE SPECIAL REFERENCE TO
COIMBATORE DISTRICT**

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1 INTRODUCTION

A College is an educational institution or a constituent part of one. A college may be a degree awarding tertiary educational institution, a part of a collegiate or federal university, an institution offering vocational education, or a secondary school. In most of the world, a college may be a high school or secondary school, a college of further education, a training institution that awards trade qualifications.

Thus, a college was a form of corporation or corporate body, an artificial legal person with its own legal personality, with the capacity to enter into legal contracts to sue and be sued. College is important for many reasons, including long term financial gain, job stability, career satisfaction and success outside of the work place. Here some reasons they are College graduates earn more on average, Workers with a college degree are less likely to face unemployment, College graduates are more likely to experience job satisfaction, A college degree can boost your financial savvy, A college degree could also mean better health, earning a college degree could even boost your happiness, earn a college education and you could even live a longer life, College degree holders are more likely to be homeowners.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

- To evaluate the level of perception and attitude of students for selecting private colleges.
- To identify the major factors influencing in students' perceptions towards among selecting the Private colleges
- To analyses the students are getting good education and facility from the colleges.
- To provide suggestion to the students for selecting the colleges.

1.3 Statement of the Problem

- Consumer preferences are vital for the success of retail chains like Big Bazaar.
- There is growing competition in the retail sector, demanding better understanding of customer behavior.
- In Coimbatore district, consumer choices vary due to diverse demographics and lifestyle patterns.
- Factors like price, quality, brand, offers, store ambience, and service affect purchasing decisions.
- There is a need to analyze how these factors influence product selection specifically at Big Bazaar.

- Limited research exists focusing solely on Big Bazaar consumers in the Coimbatore district.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

- **(Ross Baird May 2009)** This study conveys that many cost inputs—rent, salaries, and more—are substantially, proportionally lower than they would be in developed countries, and this is a primary reason why fees are so comparatively low. It is possible that private colleges are not widespread enough in developed for the market to reduce the cost of making private colleges accessible to low-income students in these countries, but this hypothesis is currently empirically unsupported.
- **(Rohaizat Baha run, Zubaidah Awang and Siti Falinda Padlee 2011)** this research is based on as the value of the education market is worth hundreds of billions of dollars in today's market, this has resulted in the announcement of a new joint-venture every week by traditional or new players all over the world, as they compete to be in the forefront of this increasingly global market.
- **(Laura Day Ashley, Claire Mcloughlin 2014)** this research is based on the Private colleges are increasingly prevalent in rural areas, but it should not be assumed that the poor are accessing these schools more.
- **(Francisco Benavides, Pauline Musset 2012)** the author conveys that In the education systems, the vast majority of students have the opportunity to attain high level skills, regardless of their own personal and socio-economic circumstances.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

A research methodology is a method for solving an issue in a systematic manner. It is one of the frameworks used to address the problem, together with the researcher's own logic. Research is a step-by-step procedure that requires precision, and it is completed when the researcher has found a suitable answer to his or her difficulties. In summary, the technique will aid in the design, execution, briefing, and bringing the study to life.

Sample size

It provides the number of respondents chosen from the colleges under study. A sample size revealed that it is most helpful when it meets the requirements for ability, stability, and flexibility. So, the researcher choose 130 samples, which were collected through proportionate sampling from respondents in selected colleges in the Coimbatore District of Tamil Nadu.

Statistical Tools Used

- **Percentage Analysis** – to understand the distribution of responses and demographic characteristics.
- **Graphical Representation** – bar charts and pie charts to visually interpret the data

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Age of the Respondents

S.NO	Age of the respondents	Number of the respondents	Percentage
1.	15-20	85	65%
2.	21-25	36	28%
3.	26-30	9	9%
4.	Above 30	Nil	Nil
	Total	130	100%

Source: Primary data

The above table 4.1 shows that, out of 130 respondents 85 of the respondents are 18-20 years, 36 of the respondents are 21-25 years, 9 of the respondents are 26-30 years, there are no respondent's for above 30 years. Hence the majority of the respondents are from 18-20 years.

Chart-4.1
Age of the Respondents

Table-4.2**Gender of the Respondents**

S.NO	Gender of the respondents	Number of the respondents	Percentage
1.	Male	77	59%
2.	Female	53	41%
3.	Transgender	Nil	Nil
	Total	130	100%

Source: Primary Data

The above table 4.2 shows that, out of 130 respondents 77 respondents are male, 53 respondents are female. **Hence the majority of the respondents are male**

Chart 4.2**Gender of the Respondents**

FINDINGS

- Majority of the respondents 65% are under 15-20 Age □ Majority of the respondents 59% are male
- Most of the respondent 44% are from the rural area

SUGGESTION

- In this study suggested the college to provide the core and subject book more for the reference of the students
- The college has to concentrate more on cleanliness and food provided in the canteen.
- The college has to provide more placement opportunity and placement training for the future of the students
- Most the colleges has sport facilities other than sports the college has to concentrate more on other extracurricular activities.

CONCLUSION

This study explored the students are choose the private colleges for their well education and career. The colleges choose by the students are well trained teaching staff .Most the students prefer private colleges. The colleges should give more awareness to the students for their career and they need to help the students to know their right path. Increase in you technique and technology will make students more knowledgeable and to know their right path of life. Colleges with supportive staff and high facilities like lab, library etc. help the students to make their life success.